

GANDHIAN APPROACH TO RURAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *Gandhian approach to rural development may be labelled as idealist . It attaches supreme importance to more values and gives supreme importance to more values and gives primacy to moral values over material conditions.*

The rural development generally refers to the process of improving the quality of life and economic well being of living in a relatively isolated and sparsely populated area. Gandhiji insisted on the self-sufficiency of Indian villages . Self sufficiency was advocated by him as a basic principle of life because dependence brings in exploitation which is the essence of violence . Rural Development in India is one of the most important factors for the growth of the Indian economy. Rural Development successfully tries to increase the productivity of those areas of rural economies that are experiencing severe poverty challenges.

INTRODUCTION:

Mahatma Gandhi had a vision to develop rural India and tried all villages to be self-dependent. One of the most important feature of rural development is the handloom industry. Handloom is unparallel in its flexibility and versatility permitting experimentation and encouraging innovations. The handloom sector of India is known all over the world for its uniqueness and intricate designs. It has established its reputation as a timeless facet of the rich cultural heritage of India.

Handloom sector is a symbol of the country's glorious cultural heritage and an important source of livelihood in the country. The sector is key to women empowerment as over 70%of handloom weavers and allied workers are women.

The first Handloom industry in India was Bhoodan Pochampally and it marked its place in Indian history as a silk mine in the 18th century. Why is it called Handloom?

Weaving a fabrics done on looms. The looms are either hand operated or power operated. Hand operated looms are called hand looms and power operated looms are called power looms.

To go back to history – Indus valley Civilization is said to the birth place of handlooms in India and is backed by strong archeological evidence, wherein excavation in the sub-continent uncovered spindles and whorls used to spin cotton back in the day.

Therefore Handloom plays a crucial role in the Indian Economy. They provide employment to millions, especially women

in rural areas, thereby empowering them . The sector is also vital for preserving traditional art forms, each region boosting distinct weaving techniques and patterns.

In addition to this the government provides handloom marketing assistance (HMA) the urban Haats scheme and handloom awards to develop the industry and encourage business in India. For the development of mega handlooms clusters, the government of India plans to provide financial assistance like Rs.10,000/-per weaver and credit guarantee for a period of 3years is also provided.

Swadeshi :

Swadeshi is the moral principle underlying a decentralized self sufficient economic structure. According to Gandhiji, “Swadeshi is that spirit in us which restrict us to the use and self-confidence of our immediate surroundings to the exclusion of the more remote.” In economic terms, a strict adherence to swadeshi doctrine paves the way to decentralized self sufficient economy. the buyers and sellers having a concern for each other , jointly work for the development of the local areas using local resources. Gandhiji emphasized, “every village of India will almost be a self supporting and self contained unit exchanging only such necessary commodities to other villages where they are not locally producible ”..

The spirit of Swadeshi guiding man’s economic behavior leads to natural love and preference for local products and an attitude of service to the immediate neighbours. The consumers, for their requirements must buy from the local producers and thus support the local farmers , artisans such as weavers, carpenters, cobblers, potters, etc., Adherence to the principle of swadeshi

leads to a natural economic order and harmony. The decentralized economic units would thus facilitate the best possible use of local raw materials, talents and man power ,promote occupational equilibrium, ecological balance and co-operative living. The village would be able to produce whatever is required, with the help of local resources and would be intended with what ever has been produced in closer surroundings Gandhiji was profoundly moved by the poverty and miserable conditions of the masses due to the centralization of the economic power in the hands of the capitalist class, He enunciated the theory of trusteeship in order to bring about the required change in a nonviolent way.

CONCLUSION:

The concept of ‘Rama Rajya’ is the basis of Gandhiji’s idea of an ideal social order. Gandhiji defined Rama Rajya as “sovereignty of the people based on moral authority”. He did not view Rama as a king, and people as his subjects , in the Gandhian Scheme, ‘Rama’ stood for god or one’s own ‘Inner voice’ Gandhi believed in a democratic social order in which people are supreme. Their supremacy is, however, not absolute. It is subject to moral values.

Gandhiji was very keen to bring about maximum regional self-sufficiency in regard to food, clothing and shelter in rural areas. To solve rural poverty, he emphasized not only agriculture but also cottage and small scale industries. He focused his attention on non-agricultural aspect of the rural economy also . He wanted diversified economic activities in the villages and thus stood for all round development of rural India.

The government also introduced integrated Handloom Development

scheme provides need based inputs to clusters of 300-500 handlooms

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